

1 **NKG7 inhibition for reversal or management of acute rejection in solid organ and hematopoietic**
2 **stem cell transplant.**

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7 I. We present here evidence supporting a proposal for experimental use of an NKG7 neutralizing
8 antibody (under development) in solid organ or HSCT transplant patients undergoing acute rejection that
9 is resistant to treatment (treatment resistant acute rejection) based on FDA Compassionate Use protocol
10 guidelines.

11 II. NKG7 inhibition for reversal or management of acute rejection in solid organs and hematopoietic
12 stem cell transplant.

13 III. Concept: NKG7 is both a marker of and transmitter of signals critical for propagation of signals
14 important for rejection.

15 IV. Challenges: Evidence suggesting NKG7 also coordinates immune-mediated clearance of
16 transformed cells suggests therapeutic NKG7 should be brief and may trigger malignancy. Given limited
17 use (in time administered and population targeted) and its potential redundancy in signaling pathways
18 important for clearance of transformed or genomically unstable cells through Tyd, NK and CD8+ and
19 HLA-V/KIR2DL3, the benefits of managing an acute rejection reaction may likely outweigh malignancy
20 associated risks and importantly serve as an introduction to development of advanced, targeting
21 therapeutics important for transplant medicine and future applications of transplant techniques in other
22 patient populations (chronic autoimmune diseases) that would otherwise be considered too risky to be
23 considered without the ability to titrate and control responses important for tolerance in the immune
24 system, a basic self non-self discrimination process.
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1 **Lymphocyte antigens are important for immunologic tolerance during organ transplant rejection.**

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7 Lymphocyte antigens are expressed on hematopoietic-derived cells. We hypothesized Ly antigen
8 expression and their associated diverse functions were important during engraftment and for
9 immunological tolerance in stem cell and solid organ transplant patients. Here we measured total
10 transcription in a tissue model of immunological tolerance disruption using skin from stem cell transplant
11 patients with sclerotic graft versus host disease (GVHD). We combined study of GVHD in hematopoietic
12 stem cell transplant patients with whole transcriptome study of solid organ transplant rejection and
13 discovered a relationship between expression of lymphocyte antigens and immunologic tolerance in
14 settings including solid organ transplant rejection and GVHD in human hematopoietic stem cell transplant.
15 Lymphocyte antigens were co-expressed with NKG7, a marker expression on the natural killer cell.
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Results

Figure 1: Ly antigen expression is dysregulated in graft versus host disease.

We measured total expression at a barrier interface in patients experiencing chronic graft versus host disease following reconstitution of the hematopoietic system after receiving a stem cell transplant.

a. The lymphocyte antigen LY96 is activated in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
23643	6.71E-06	0.4648	-4.502691	-2.09270785	293.34	LY96	1097/21972	

b. The lymphocyte antigen LY6G6D is repressed in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
58530	2.21E-05	0.869	4.242784	3.68687431	167.02	LY6G6D	1368/21972	

c. The lymphocyte antigen LY86 is activated in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
9450	5.93E-05	0.4407	-4.015597	-1.7696102	194.08	LY86	1664/21972	

d. The lymphocyte antigen LY6G6F is repressed in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
259215	5.41E-03	0.468	2.781448	1.30175864	17.45	LY6G6F	4649/21972	

e. The lymphocyte antigen LY75 is repressed in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
4065	2.48E-02	0.2685	-2.244188	-0.60260764	700.75	LY75	6757/21972	

f. The lymphocyte antigen LY6G5B is repressed in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
58496	3.29E-02	0.23	2.133261	0.49061921	1418.74	LY6G5B	7309/21972	

g. The lymphocyte antigen LY6E is repressed in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
4061	6.64E-02	0.2254	1.835578	0.41369905	6916.78	LY6E	8843/21972	

h. TSLP is activated in the tissues of patients undergoing active GVHD.

<u>GeneID</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>lfcSE</u>	<u>stat</u>	<u>log2FoldChange</u>	<u>baseMean</u>	<u>Gene</u>	<u>Rank</u>	<u>%DE</u>
85480	3.52E-07	0.3566	-5.093185	-1.81601184	94.31	TSLP	610/21972	

Figure 2: Lymphocyte antigen expression is dysregulated in the peripheral blood of kidney transplant patients undergoing acute rejection.

a. LY75 is repressed in the peripheral blood of kidney transplant patients during acute rejection.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205668_at	0.00007235	4.1872077	1.15607	1.04868138	LY75	18/54675	

b. LY6D is repressed in the peripheral blood of kidney transplant patients during acute rejection.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
206276_at	0.09358951	-1.6970678	-4.32495	-0.14669009	LY6D	8157/54675	

c. LY86 is repressed in the peripheral blood of kidney transplant patients during acute rejection.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205859_at	0.06460138	1.8739788	-4.0659	0.28397717	LY86	5887/54675	

Figure 3: Lymphocyte antigens are dysregulated in the organs of transplant patients with acute rejection.

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We compared kidney biopsy tissue from $n=60$ patients with no or stable rejection ($n=60$) and $n=4$ patients with acute rejection (TCMR=4).

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205859_at	6.13e-12	-8.3788779	16.9336	-2.00486895	LY86	102/	
231124_x_at	4.20e-06	-5.0240974	4.011265	-1.31117412	LY9	1089/	
206584_at	7.35e-06	-4.8738028	3.476776	-2.66995459	LY96	1210/	
203799_at	6.39e-05	-4.2744268	1.424207	-1.27129767	LY75-CD302	1832/	
205668_at	7.99e-04	-3.5176056	-0.943664	-1.50274204	LY75	3117/	
202145_at	4.34e-03	-2.9556045	-2.498184	-0.54935536	LY6E	4808/54675	

Figure 4: The natural killer cell activation marker NKG7 is co-regulated with the lymphocyte antigen family.

1 NKG7 is a marker of the natural killer cell (10). Natural killer cells are described to function in tolerogenic
2 settings (10).

3 **Discussion**

4 We described here dysregulation of Ly antigen during transplant rejection of a solid organ and during graft
5 versus host disease following hematopoietic stem cell transplant.

6 We recently demonstrated that the innate immune pattern recognition receptor NOD2 controlled Ly
7 antigen expression which was altered upon expression of a NOD2 mutant whose polymorphism is
8 associated with transplant related mortality. The cytokine TSLP was also a NOD2 transcriptional target.

9 Together we have described a role for NOD2 in regulation of immunological tolerance during stem cell and
10 solid organ transplant through diverse functions of the Ly antigen family.

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